

STABILITY OF A BECK-TYPE LAMINATED COLUMN

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ABSTRACT

In this paper an analytical method for calculating the stability of a laminated column under a Beck-type load is proposed with shear deformation and rotatory inertia being taken into account of. Emphasis is placed on discussion of the effect of fibre orientation on the critical values of the column. An example is given and the results indicate that for a laminated column of greater ratio of slenderness the effect of ply angle of fibres on actual critical values is mainly reflected by that on bending stiffness of the column.

INTRODUCTION

Various problems of mechanics have been encountered as composite materials find more and more applications in engineering. The stability of nonconservative structural systems is a kind of important problems in aeronautical and astronautical engineering in which great importance is especially attached to the applications of composite materials. Therefore investigations on stability of composite structure under nonconservative loads have been called for and deserves attention. At present time there have been much work on composite material mechanics or nonconservative systems, but the work related to both has not yet been found in the literature.

As a part of our research on stability of composite structures, this paper presents discussions of stability of a laminated column with one end fixed and the other free

under a Beck-type nonconservative load, which we call a Beck-type laminated column. The dynamic equation and boundary conditions of the system are deduced from a virtual-work-type Hamilton principle, and the characteristic equation is obtained with shear deformation and rotatory inertia being considered. The effect of the fibre ply angle of the column on its critical values is studied with a numerical example.

For sake of simplicity and without losing generality, the discussion of the paper is restricted to a symmetrical cross-ply laminated column with a Beck-type follower force.

CONSTITUTIVE EQUATIONS

The deflection of the column axis is shown in Fig. 1. The load P is a follower force with the line of action always coincident with the tangential line of the column axis at its free end during motion. Suppose a cross-ply laminated column is made up of n plies of fibres and all lie symmetrically to the principal plane x - y . There are two ply orientations in each single ply which have the same magnitude but opposite sign, that is, the ply angles with x axis of a ply are $+\theta_i$ and $-\theta_i$.

Fig. 1. Deflection of column axis.

The generalized forces when the column vibrates are bending moment M and shear force Q , and the corresponding generalized displacements are rotating angle of cross section around y axis ϕ and deflection along z axis W . All of these quantities are functions of coordinate x and time t . The constitutive equations of the column are written as

$$M = -D \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x}, \quad Q = KC \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial x} - \phi \right), \quad (1)$$

where D , C are bending stiffness and shear stiffness, respectively, K shear coefficient. Assume that the constants of material for the i -th ply are E_1^i , E_2^i , E_3^i , G_{12}^i , G_{23}^i , G_{31}^i , ν_{12}^i , ν_{23}^i , ν_{31}^i . The coordinates 1, 2, 3 are the principal directions of material. Considering that the column is subjected to compressive force, we suppose σ_y , σ_z can be ignored compared with σ_x . Then we have

$$D = \frac{1}{3} \sum_1^n 2b_i (z_i^3 - z_{i-1}^3) / \left[\frac{1}{E_1^i} \cos^4 \theta_i + \frac{1}{E_1^i} \sin^4 \theta_i + \left(\frac{1}{G_{12}^i} - 2 \frac{\nu_{12}^i}{E_1^i} \right) \cos^2 \theta_i \sin^2 \theta_i \right], \quad (2)$$

$$C = \sum_1^n 2b_i h_i / \left(\frac{1}{G_{23}^i} \sin^2 \theta_i + \frac{1}{G_{31}^i} \cos^2 \theta_i \right) \quad (3)$$

where b_i , h_i are, respectively, the width and thickness of the i -th ply.

EQUATIONS OF MOTION

There is no functional of total potential energy for a nonconservative system and the usual variational principles can not be utilized. However principle of virtual work always holds. For the dynamic system studied here the following Hamilton principle of virtual-work-type may be used.

$$\delta U - \delta T = \delta V \quad (4)$$

where δU , δT , and δV are the incrementals of strain energy, kinematical energy, and work of external force, respectively. They are expressed as follows

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \int_0^l \left[D \left(\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x} \right)^2 + KC \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial x} - \Phi \right)^2 \right] dx dt, \quad (5)$$

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \int_0^l \left[\rho A \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \rho I \left(\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} \right)^2 \right] dx dt, \quad (6)$$

$$V = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \left\{ \int_0^l \frac{1}{2} P \delta \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial x} \right)^2 dx - P \frac{\partial W}{\partial x} \delta W \Big|_{x=l} \right\} dt \quad (7)$$

where l is length of the column, ρ mass density, A area of cross section, and I rotatory inertia of cross section around

y axis.

Substituting Eqs. (5), (6), (7) into Eq. (4) and using variational calculations, we obtain the equations of motion for the column:

$$D \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x^2} + KC \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial x} - \Phi \right) - \rho I \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial t^2} = 0, \quad (8)$$

$$KC \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial x} - \Phi \right) - \rho A \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial t^2} - P \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial x^2} = 0, \quad (9)$$

and the boundary conditions:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \text{at } x=0, \quad W = \Phi = 0, \\ \text{at } x=1, \quad M = -D \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x} = 0, \quad Q = KC \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial x} - \Phi \right) = 0. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (10)$$

CHARACTERISTIC EQUATION

Combining Eq. (8) with Eq. (9), we get

$$\frac{\partial^4 W}{\partial x^4} + \frac{\rho A}{\eta D} \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial t^2} - \left(\frac{\rho A}{KC} + \frac{\rho I}{D} \right) \frac{\partial^4 W}{\partial x^2 \partial t^2} + \frac{P}{\eta D} \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\rho I \rho A}{D KC} \frac{\partial^4 W}{\partial t^4} = 0 \quad (11)$$

where $\eta = 1 - P/KC$. Letting

$$W(x, t) = w(x) e^{i\omega t}, \quad (12)$$

and introducing nondimensional quantities $\xi = x/l$ and

$$\text{stiffness ratio } \mathcal{E} = D/KCl^2, \quad (13)$$

$$\text{slender ratio } r = 2(AI^2/I)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (14)$$

$$\text{load parameter } S = Pl^2/D, \quad (15)$$

$$\text{frequency parameter } \Omega^2 = \rho Al^4 \omega^2/D, \quad (16)$$

Eq. (11) changes into

$$\frac{\partial^4 w(\xi)}{\partial \xi^4} + \beta^2 \frac{\partial^2 w(\xi)}{\partial \xi^2} - \gamma w(\xi) = 0, \quad (17)$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \beta^2 &= (\Omega^2 \mathcal{E} + S) / (1 - S\mathcal{E}) + 4\Omega^2/r, \\ \gamma &= \Omega^2 (1 - 4\Omega^2 \mathcal{E}/r^2) / (1 - S\mathcal{E}). \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (18)$$

The general solution of Eq. (17) is

$$w(\xi) = C_1 \cosh \bar{\lambda} \xi + C_2 \sinh \bar{\lambda} \xi + C_3 \cos \lambda \xi + C_4 \sin \lambda \xi, \quad (19)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda &= [(\beta^4/4 + \nu)^{1/2} + \beta^2/2]^{1/2}, \\ \bar{\lambda} &= [(\beta^4/4 + \nu)^{1/2} - \beta^2/2]^{1/2}. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The boundary conditions (10) changes into

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \text{at } \xi = 0, \quad w(\xi) = \varphi(\xi) = 0, \\ \text{at } \xi = 1, \quad m(\xi) = q(\xi) = 0, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (21)$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} q(\xi) &= -(\eta D/l^3)/(1 - 4\Omega^2 \varepsilon/r^2) \{ w'''(\xi) + \frac{\Omega^2}{\eta} (\varepsilon + 4/r^2) w'(\xi) \}, \\ m(\xi) &= -(\eta D/l^2) \{ w''(\xi) + \frac{1}{\eta} \Omega^2 \varepsilon w(\xi) \}, \\ \varphi(\xi) &= (1/l) \{ w'(\xi) - lq(\xi)/K_C \}. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (22)$$

With substitution of Eq. (19) into Eq. (21), the characteristic equation of the system is obtained:

$$\begin{vmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & (1 + \Omega^2 \varepsilon^2 + \eta \varepsilon \bar{\lambda}^2) \bar{\lambda} \\ (\Omega^2 \varepsilon / \eta + \bar{\lambda}^2) \cosh \bar{\lambda} & (\Omega^2 \varepsilon / \eta + \bar{\lambda}^2) \sinh \bar{\lambda} \\ (4\Omega^2 / \eta r^2 + \Omega^2 \varepsilon / \eta + \bar{\lambda}^2) \bar{\lambda} \sinh \bar{\lambda} & (4\Omega^2 / \eta r^2 + \Omega^2 \varepsilon / \eta + \bar{\lambda}^2) \bar{\lambda} \cosh \bar{\lambda} \\ 1 & 0 \\ 0 & (1 + \Omega^2 \varepsilon^2 - \eta \varepsilon \lambda^2) \lambda \\ (\Omega^2 \varepsilon / \eta - \lambda^2) \cos \lambda & (\Omega^2 \varepsilon / \eta - \lambda^2) \sin \lambda \\ (-4\Omega^2 / \eta r^2 - \Omega^2 \varepsilon / \eta + \lambda^2) \lambda \sin \lambda & (4\Omega^2 / \eta r^2 + \Omega^2 \varepsilon / \eta - \lambda^2) \lambda \cos \lambda \end{vmatrix} = 0. \quad (23)$$

This may be simply written as:

$$F(\Omega^2, S, \theta, r, K) = 0. \quad (24)$$

It is seen that the characteristic equation of the column is a transcendental function of load, frequency, ply angle, slender ratio, and shear coefficient when the material constants of each ply are given.

When $K \rightarrow \infty$ and $r \rightarrow \infty$, Eq. (24) degenerates into the characteristic equation of a Beck column according to the classical beam theory $F(\Omega^2, S) = 0$, which is a function of the non-dimensional frequency and load.

After solving the nondimensional frequency Ω^2 and load S from Eq. (24), the actual frequency ω and load P can be calculated from the following formulae:

$$\omega = \sqrt{\Omega^2 D / \rho A l^4}, \quad (25)$$

$$P = SD / l^2. \quad (26)$$

The characteristic curves $S - \Omega^2$ and $P - \omega$ are easy to be drawn, from the vertexes of which the critical frequency Ω_{cr}^2 (ω_{cr}) load S_{cr} (P_{cr}) may be determined.

EXAMPLE AND DISCUSSIONS

Taking a single ply column of rectangular cross section as an example, the critical values with different ply angles are calculated. The material constants are $E_1 = 3.5672 \times 10^4$ N/cm², $E_2 = E_3 = 1.0388 \times 10^4$ N/cm², $G_{12} = 4.6354 \times 10^3$ N/cm², $G_{23} = 3.8514 \times 10^3$ N/cm², $G_{31} = 4.6354 \times 10^3$ N/cm², $\rho = 1.86 \times 10^{-3}$ Kg/cm³, $\nu = 0.33$. The geometric quantities are $b = 2$ cm, $h = 0.5$ cm, $l = 20$ cm, $K = 0.186$.

Fig. 2 shows the characteristic curves with different ply angles. It can be seen that the ply angle θ has remarkable effect on the actual critical values of the column. The actual critical load P_{cr} and frequency ω_{cr} at $\theta = 0^\circ$ are greater than those at other values of θ . This can be visualized because the bending stiffness D is the greatest at $\theta = 0^\circ$. The values of P_{cr} at $\theta = 15^\circ$, 30° , 60° , and 90° are, respectively, 76.55%, 49.22%, 31.45%, and 30.34% of that at $\theta = 0^\circ$. The analogous percentages of the critical frequency ω_{cr} are 87.68%, 70.47%, 56.41%, and 55.48%.

From Eq. (24), one may see that the ply angle θ has effect on the nondimensional frequency and load, because it affects the stiffness ratio ξ . Also, the actual critical frequency ω_{cr} and load P_{cr} determined from Eqs. (25) and (26) depend on the bending stiffness D . Therefore we say that the ply angle θ has double effects on the actual cri-

Fig. 2. Characteristic curves with different ply angles.

tical values. The characteristics of variation of nondimensional critical load S_{cr} and frequency Ω_{cr}^2 with the slender ratio r at different ply angles are shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, respectively. In this calculation, $h=0.57735\text{cm}$, $l=5\text{--}25\text{cm}$. It can be seen from the figures that both of S_{cr} and Ω_{cr}^2 increase with r , although the rates of change are small. Moreover the differences of them at different values of θ decrease as r gets large. Particularly, at greater values of r the differences are very small, and thus we may hold that the effect of ply angle θ on actual critical values is mainly reflected by that of it on bending stiffness D .

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The stability of a Beck-type laminated column was investigated in the present paper. Much attention was paid to the effect of ply angle on critical values of the system. The analytical results indicate the follows:

Fig. 3. Characteristics of variation of nondimensional critical load S_{cr} with slender ratio r .

Fig. 4. Characteristics of variation of nondimensional critical frequency Ω_{cr}^2 with slender ratio r .

(1) the ply angle θ has remarkable effect on the actual critical frequency ω_{cr} and load P_{cr} , the values of which are the greatest at $\theta=0^\circ$;

(2) for definite values of the shear coefficient K , the

effect of ply angle θ on actual critical values is mainly reflected by that of it on bending stiffness D when the slender ratio r gets larger.

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